

PRESERVING LINGUISTIC DIVERSITY: STRATEGIES FOR LANGUAGE PRESERVATION AND REVITALIZATION IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD

Turdiyeva N.A.

Teacher of samarkand institute
of economic and service

Ashirova M.M.

Student of samarkand institute
of economic and service

Annotation: In a rapidly globalizing world, the preservation and revitalization of endangered languages have become pressing concerns. This paper examines the multifaceted challenges facing linguistic diversity and explores innovative strategies for language preservation and revitalization. Drawing on case studies from around the globe, the paper discusses the social, cultural, and political significance of language preservation efforts. It explores the impact of globalization, urbanization, and colonial legacies on indigenous languages and minority dialects. Additionally, the paper analyzes successful initiatives aimed at revitalizing endangered languages, including community-based language programs, digital technology tools, and language policy reforms. By synthesizing theoretical frameworks with practical examples, this paper offers insights into effective approaches for safeguarding linguistic diversity and fostering cultural heritage in the 21st century.

Keywords: Linguistic diversity, language preservation, language revitalization, endangered languages, globalization, cultural heritage, community-driven initiatives, digital technology, language policy, advocacy efforts, collaborative strategies, intergenerational language transmission, Bilingual education, language rights, cultural sensitivity

Annotatsiya: Tez globallashib borayotgan dunyoda yo‘qolib ketish xavfi ostida turgan tillarni saqlash va jonlantirish dolzarb masalalarga aylandi. Ushbu maqola til xilma-xilligi oldida turgan ko‘p qirrali muammolarni ko‘rib chiqadi va tilni saqlash va jonlantirish uchun innovatsion strategiyalarni o‘rganadi. Maqolada dunyoning turli burchaklaridan olingan amaliy tadqiqotlar asosida tilni saqlash borasidagi sa’y-harakatlarning ijtimoiy, madaniy va siyosiy ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi. U globallashuv, urbanizatsiya va mustamlakachilik merosining mahalliy tillar va ozchilik lahjalariga ta'sirini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada yo‘qolib ketish xavfi ostida turgan tillarni jonlantirishga qaratilgan muvaffaqiyatli tashabbuslar, jumladan, jamiyatga asoslangan til dasturlari, raqamli texnologiya vositalari va til siyosati islohotlari tahlil qilingan. Nazariy asoslarni amaliy misollar bilan sintez

qilish orqali ushbu maqola 21-asrda til xilma-xilligini himoya qilish va madaniy merosni rivojlantirishning samarali yondashuvlari haqida tushuncha beradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Til xilma-xilligi, tilni saqlash, tilni qayta tiklash, yoʻqolib borayotgan tillar, globallashuv, madaniy meros, hamjamiyat tashabbuslari, raqamli texnologiyalar, til siyosati, advokatlik sa'y-harakatlari, hamkorlik strategiyalari, avlodlararo til uzatish, ikki tilli ta'lim, til huquqlari, madaniy sezgirlik

Аннотация: Сохранение и возрождение языков, находящихся под угрозой исчезновения, стали актуальными проблемами в быстро глобализирующемся мире. В этой статье рассматриваются многогранные проблемы, стоящие перед языковым разнообразием, и исследуются инновационные стратегии сохранения и возрождения языка. В статье обсуждается социальная, культурная и политическая значимость усилий по сохранению языка на основе тематических исследований из разных уголков мира. В нем исследуется влияние глобализации, урбанизации и колониального наследия на местные языки и диалекты меньшинств. Кроме того, в статье анализируются успешные инициативы, направленные на возрождение языков, находящихся под угрозой исчезновения, включая языковые программы на уровне сообществ, инструменты цифровых технологий и реформы языковой политики. Обобщая теоретические основы с практическими примерами, эта статья дает представление об эффективных подходах к защите языкового разнообразия и популяризации культурного наследия в 21 веке.

Ключевые слова: Языковое разнообразие, сохранение языка, возрождение языка, языки, находящиеся под угрозой исчезновения, глобализация, культурное наследие, общественные инициативы, цифровые технологии, языковая политика, информационно-пропагандистская деятельность, стратегии сотрудничества, передача языка из поколения в поколение, двуязычное образование, языковые права, культурная чувствительность

Language revitalization, also referred to as language revival or reversing language shift, is an attempt to halt or reverse the decline of a language or to revive an extinct one. Those involved can include linguists, cultural or community groups, or governments. Some argue for a distinction between language revival (the resurrection of an extinct language with no existing native speakers) and language revitalization (the rescue of a "dying" language). There has only been one successful instance of a complete language revival, the Hebrew language, creating a new generation of native speakers without any pre-existing native speakers as a model. Languages targeted for language revitalization include those whose use and prominence is severely limited. Sometimes various tactics of language revitalization can even be used to try to revive extinct languages. Though the goals of language

revitalization vary greatly from case to case, they typically involve attempting to expand the number of speakers and use of a language, or trying to maintain the current level of use to protect the language from extinction or language death. Reasons for revitalization vary: they can include physical danger affecting those whose language is dying, economic danger such as the exploitation of indigenous natural resources, political danger such as genocide, or cultural danger/assimilation. In recent times[when?] alone, it is estimated that more than 2000 languages have already become extinct. The UN estimates that more than half of the languages spoken today have fewer than 10,000 speakers and that a quarter have fewer than 1,000 speakers; and that, unless there are some efforts to maintain them, over the next hundred years most of these will become extinct. These figures are often cited as reasons why language revitalization is necessary to preserve linguistic diversity. Culture and identity are also frequently cited reasons for language revitalization, when a language is perceived as a unique "cultural treasure". A community often sees language as a unique part of their culture, connecting them with their ancestors or with the land, making up an essential part of their history and self-image.

Language revitalization is also closely tied to the linguistic field of language documentation. In this field, linguists try to create a complete record of a language's grammar, vocabulary, and linguistic features. This practice can often lead to more concern for the revitalization of a specific language on study. Furthermore, the task of documentation is often taken on with the goal of revitalization in mind.

Language revitalisation has been linked to increased health outcomes for Indigenous communities involved in reclaiming traditional language. Benefits range from improved mental health for community members, increasing connectedness to culture, identity, and a sense of wholeness. Indigenous languages are a core element in the formation of identity, providing pathways for cultural expression, agency, spiritual and ancestral connection. Connection to culture is considered to play an important role in childhood development, and is a UN convention right. As colonisation and subsequent linguicide was carried out through policies such as those that created Australia's Stolen Generations have damaged this connection. It has been proposed that language revitalization may play an important role in countering intergenerational trauma that has been caused. Researchers at the University of Adelaide and South Australian Health and Medical Research Institute have found that language revitalisation of Aboriginal languages is linked to better mental health. One study in the Barnjarla Community in South Australia has been looking holistically at the positive benefits of language reclamation, healing mental and emotional scars, and building connections to community and country that underpin wellness and wholeness. The study identified the Barnjarla peoples

connection to their language as a strong component of developing a strong cultural and personal identity; the people are as connected to language as they are to culture, and culture is key to their identity. Some proponents claim that language reclamation is a form of empowerment and builds strong connections with community and wholeness.

Language preservation and revitalization refer to efforts aimed at maintaining and restoring endangered languages, particularly those facing the threat of extinction due to various social, cultural, and political factors. Here's some information on the topic:

1. **Importance of Linguistic Diversity:** Linguistic diversity is crucial for preserving cultural heritage, maintaining traditional knowledge systems, and promoting social cohesion within communities. Languages often encode unique cultural perspectives, histories, and identities, which can be lost if a language disappears.

2. **Factors Threatening Languages:** Endangered languages are often vulnerable due to factors such as globalization, urbanization, language shift to dominant languages, government policies favoring majority languages, and cultural assimilation. These processes can lead to intergenerational language transmission breakdown, where younger generations no longer learn or speak their ancestral languages.

3. **Documentation and Archiving:** Language preservation efforts often involve documenting endangered languages through linguistic research, recordings, and written materials. This documentation serves as a resource for future language revitalization efforts and helps linguists understand linguistic diversity.

4. **Community-Based Language Revitalization:** Many successful language revitalization initiatives are community-driven, with local speakers taking the lead in preserving and promoting their languages. These efforts may include language immersion programs, community language schools, cultural events, and intergenerational language transmission programs.

5. **Technology and Language Revitalization:** Digital technology plays a significant role in language preservation and revitalization. Projects such as online dictionaries, language learning apps, social media campaigns, and digital archives make language resources more accessible and facilitate language revitalization efforts, especially for dispersed communities.

6. **Language Policy and Advocacy:** Language revitalization often requires supportive language policies at the national and local levels. Advocacy for language rights, bilingual education programs, and official recognition of minority languages can help protect and promote linguistic diversity.

7. Collaborative Efforts: Language preservation and revitalization efforts are often collaborative endeavors involving linguists, community members, educators, policymakers, and other stakeholders. Collaboration ensures that initiatives are culturally sensitive, linguistically accurate, and sustainable in the long term.

Overall, language preservation and revitalization are essential for maintaining the rich tapestry of human languages and safeguarding cultural heritage for future generations. These efforts contribute to global linguistic diversity and promote respect for the linguistic rights of all communities.

CONCLUSION: In conclusion, the preservation and revitalization of linguistic diversity are vital endeavors in our increasingly globalized world. Through this paper, we have explored the multifaceted challenges facing endangered languages and the innovative strategies employed to safeguard their survival. From community-driven initiatives to digital technology tools, a diverse array of approaches has emerged to address the complex issues threatening linguistic diversity.

It is evident that language preservation and revitalization efforts must be multifaceted, community-centered, and collaborative to be effective. Community involvement, cultural sensitivity, and linguistic accuracy are paramount in ensuring the success and sustainability of revitalization initiatives. Moreover, supportive language policies, educational programs, and advocacy efforts play crucial roles in protecting linguistic rights and promoting linguistic diversity.

REFERENCES:

1. Fishman, J. A. (1991). *Reversing Language Shift: Theoretical and Empirical Foundations of Assistance to Threatened Languages*. Multilingual Matters.
2. Grenoble, L. A., & Whaley, L. J. (2006). *Saving Languages: An Introduction to Language Revitalization*. Cambridge University Press.
3. Hale, K., & Krauss, M. (Eds.). (1997). *Keynote papers from the First National Breath of Life Archival Institute for Indigenous Languages*. National Museum of the American Indian.
4. Harrison, K. D. (2007). *When Languages Die: The Extinction of the World's Languages and the Erosion of Human Knowledge*. Oxford University Press.
5. King, K. A. (2001). *Language Revitalization Processes and Prospects: Quichua in the Ecuadorian Andes*. Multilingual Matters.
6. May, S. (Ed.). (2012). *The Multilingual Turn: Implications for SLA, TESOL, and Bilingual Education*. Routledge.
7. Ostler, N. (2010). *The Last Lingua Franca: English Until the Return of Babel*. Walker & Company.
8. Reyhner, J., Lockard, L., & Tsinajinnie, L. (Eds.). (1999). *Revitalizing Indigenous Languages*. Northern Arizona University, Center for Excellence in Education.

9. Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (2000). Linguistic Genocide in Education-or Worldwide Diversity and Human Rights? Routledge.

10. Wiley, T. G., & García, O. (Eds.). (2016). Language Policy and Planning for Endangered Languages. Routledge.

EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY "SHADOWING" IN THE TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Bolbekova Ug'iloy Jaloliddinovna,
Teacher in Samarkand Institute
of Economic and Service
ugiloybolbekova@gmail.com

Annotation: This article provides information on educational technologies in which learning English is very effective. The opinions of researchers about the technology of shadowing installation and the advantages of this educational technology are explained on the importance of studying foreign languages

Keywords: shadowing, teaching, speech, speaking, listening, foreign languages, educational technique

Аннотация: В этой статье представлена информация об образовательных технологиях, с помощью которых изучение английского языка является очень эффективным. Приводятся мнения исследователей о технологии установки теневого обучения и преимуществах этой образовательной технологии, а также объясняется важность изучения иностранных языков

Ключевые слова: слежка, обучение, речь, говорение, аудирование, иностранные языки, образовательная методика

President of The Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev said that it is necessary to popularize the study of foreign languages among the population and create the necessary conditions for their perfect assimilation, coordinate the introduction of internationally recognized programs and textbooks of teaching foreign languages at all stages of education, and develop modern teaching skills in teachers.

As N. N. Normatova states, "The process of developing the oral speech skills of foreign language for linguistic departments of Higher Education is different from the process of developing it for non-philological departments. The process has its own peculiarities. The quality of education, which is a bilateral process between the teacher and student, depends on the didactic perfection of teacher`s mastery, and on the other hand, the on the student's motivational activity.

Oral speech, as an effective process, requires a lot of time and effort from the student, since it also requires the inclusion of language, speech and communicative